

TYPES OF GEOGRAPHIC ATLASES AND GLOBES

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Abstract: This article talks about atlases and their types and their types, globes and their types and their importance.

Keyword: Atlas, globe, map, textbooks.

Atlases are a set of cards with complete and accurate information, organized on the basis of a single program. The term "atlas" was introduced by the Flemish cartographer Mercator. He named his collection of cards (1595) after the legendary king of Libya, Atlas. The deck of cards was first compiled by Claudius Ptolemy in the II century. Atlases are divided into atlases of planets, world, continents, oceans, countries, states, regions, depending on the area they occupy. Depending on the content, it is divided into general geographical and thematic atlases. According to the task, it is divided into scientific, informative, popular (local history), educational, tourist and road atlases.

Globes and their types

A globe (Latin globe - round) is a miniature copy of the Earth, in which the shape of the Earth's surface, seas and oceans, mountains and plains are accurately and accurately depicted. For the first time, the globe was made by Beruni in the 10th century, and by Beheim in the 15th century. Globes are divided into small (1:3000000) and large globes according to their scale. Large globes are made for educational and other purposes.

Types of school geographic maps.

The difference between school geographic cards and other cards is that they are adapted to the age and development of students. Simpler, easier to understand and read flashcards are released for elementary students, while more complex flashcards are released for higher grades.

Below are the cards used in general education schools we can be divided into groups:

-wall cards;

- cards in textbooks;
- atlases;
- globes;
- striped cards.

According to the content, wall school cards are very diverse: natural; climatic; soil, plant; zoogeographic; geological; minerals; economic, political, industrial; agriculture, transport. Although they are different, they also have common similarities. All of them are used in the classroom, can be adapted to the distance vision of students, that is, the scale is large. With the help of these cards, students perform practical and independent work in learning knowledge and answer certain questions. Therefore, they should be of a size that has good visibility and high resolution. Depending on the type of cards, their sizes are different. Cards of the world, cards of individual continents are currently issued in the size of 1.5x1.8m. Cards of Uzbekistan and Central Asia are issued almost in this size. Cards must be clearly visible. Students should be able to clearly see the geographical event and existence in them from 5-6 m. For this, the most important things are displayed on the card. For example, when depicting a river, its main body and largest tributaries are shown, but small tributaries are not shown. Colors should be chosen well so that the card looks clear. Colors should be sharply distinguished from each other. Another requirement for wall cards is that they should be beautiful. If the card is made beautifully and clearly, students will easily read and understand them. On school cards, relief is mainly done by coloring in different thicknesses. Lowlands are given in dark green, plains in light green, highlands in light brown, medium mountains in brown, and high mountains in dark brown. The map should not be filled with geographical names. It should contain only notes that are suitable for the age and level of knowledge of the students. Geographical names can be written less and larger on cards of the primary class, and their number increases and their size decreases in the middle and upper classes. Cards to put in textbooks. A separate card was attached at the end of geography subjects. Currently, cards are given in the text of the textbooks. Such cards depict natural geographical and economic geographical events and phenomena. They can be black and white and colored. Natural geographic maps are often issued in color. Some economic geographic maps are often issued in color. Some are used. For example, minerals, sports, certain crops, livestock cards and political cards are given in color. In most cases, more cards are given in the textbooks of natural geography of continents and oceans (grade 6), world economic and social geography (grade 9).

Atlases are cards compiled on a certain topic and directions

is a sum. Atlases are divided into the following types according to their structure and content: according to their area; star atlas; natural geographic atlas of the world; world economic geographic atlas; atlas of separate continents and oceans; atlas of individual countries; according to the content: natural geographical; economic; railway; educational atlases. There are study atlases for each class. for example 5th grade atlas, 6th grade atlas, 7th grade atlas, 8th grade atlas, 9th grade atlas. Educational atlases must meet the following requirements:

- the number of geographical entities and events shown in the atlas is higher than in the textbook

there should be more;

- the atlas should serve as a reference for students;

- the list of geographical names must be included in the atlas;

The number of cards in the atlas should not be less than 40-45. Line cards. They are widely used in geography education. They are mainly used for educational and control purposes. Line cards are used for educational purposes in the following cases:

- recording the names of natural geographical entities on a linear map

(river, lake, sea, etc.), which allows geographical names to be well remembered by students;

- drawing the boundaries of mountains, river basins, isotherms, natural zones on a linear map;

- draw the borders of states on a linear map;

-reduction of economic regions on a linear map;

- drawing the boundaries of agricultural crops on a linear map.

Line cards are also used for control purposes. For this, the following conditions must be met:

- all students in the class must have the same line card;

- it is necessary to give the same conditional marks for all students;

- the scale, legend, name of the student should be shown in the same place on the line cards of all students.

Card interpretation technology.

In general education schools, teaching students to understand the structure of maps plays an important role in acquiring geographical knowledge.

In order to teach students to explain the structure of geographic maps, practical work is carried out on site, working with a site plan, practical work on reading horizontals, practicing with a level grid, comparing different maps, determining the

geographic coordinates of points, practiced with different scales. The best way to understand the cards is to study the location and determine how it is depicted on the card. In addition, moving from a globe to a map, from a plan to a geographic map, also helps to understand the structure of geographic maps. With the help of these methods, students will be able to explain level grid, cartographic zooming (generalization) and geographic maps. On-site and classroom hands-on activities (finding directions, measuring distances and plotting them, and putting them on a site plan) encourage students to gain confidence that geographic maps actually depict things and events. Understanding the structure of geographical maps is not only the work carried out on the site, but also working with the outline plan of the site. Such work is carried out during educational trips, tourist trips and practical work on site. Students will learn the structure of large-scale maps during exercises on reading horizontals, during the process of drawing a relief image with the help of topographic maps, during the creation of a site plan.

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